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Research Article

**PUBLIC AWARENESS ABOUT KIDNEY STONE DISEASE
CAUSES, MANAGEMENT AND PREVENTION METHODS
AMONG ADULT SAUDI POPULATION****Hanin A. Shalaby^{1*}, Rawan A. Obaid², Noura A. Baroom², Dr. Suhair Al-Tayyar³,
Dr. Abdulaziz Al-Ghamdi⁴**¹Department of Research Centre, King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital, Jeddah, KSA²Department of Health Education, King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital, Jeddah, KSA³Department of Family Medicine, King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital, Jeddah, KSA²Department of Urology, King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital, Jeddah, KSA**Article Received:** December 2019 **Accepted:** January 2020 **Published:** February 2020**Abstract:**

Background: Kidney stone disease (KSD) is a significant health problem that represents a recurrent condition with a major impact on a patient's quality of life. Kidney stones (KS) are described as a hard deposit of minerals and salts formed inside the kidneys.

Methods: This study employs a descriptive research method, using an online cross-sectional community-based survey to assess the level of public awareness and knowledge of KSD. The survey was applied to a Saudi adult population during the period from June to September 2019.

Results: Participants had a poor practice score (8.82 out of a possible 23 units). Although the vast majority of the participants (86%) were aware that drinking plenty of fluids prevents the formation of stones, only 6% were correct about barley and 12% were correct about cranberry juice (as preventing the formation of stones)

Conclusions: To summarize, it was found that the majority of the participants in this study showed moderate knowledge when it comes to KS disease, causes, symptoms, risk factors and prevention methods; however, there was poor management in their practice.

Keywords: Kidney stone, KS, public awareness, stone prevention, KSD in Saudi Arabia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Kidney stone disease (KSD) is a significant health problem that represents a recurrent condition with a major impact on a patient's quality of life.[1, 2,3] Kidney stones (KS) are described as a hard deposit of minerals and salts formed inside the kidneys.[4, 2] KSD is also called renal stone, urolithiasis or nephrolithiasis disease.[3,2]

Based on the available literature, the prevalence of KSD has increased by almost 70% over the past 15 years throughout the world. [3, 1] For example, in Asian countries, the percentage range of KSD increased from 1% to 5%, while in Europe, it increased from 5% to 10%. Furthermore, it is estimated that around 13% of North Americans are affected by kidney stone formation.[5] These differences are related to various factors prevalent in the regions, such as socio-economic conditions, age, sex, occupation, social class, climate, dietary habits, etc. In general, KSD is more predominant in males than females, affecting up to 10%-12% of men and 5%-6% of women.[5]

In Asia, the stone-forming belt has been reported to stretch from Sudan across to Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, the Islamic Republic of Iran, Pakistan, India, Myanmar, Thailand, Indonesia, and all the way to the Philippines.[6]

In Saudi Arabia, KSD represents a significant health problem, as it affects a much higher rate of Saudi people than in the West. In viewing the epidemiological factors, a study conducted in Riyadh in 2004 reported that Saudis are 2.5 times more prone than non-Saudis to developing kidney stones.[7] In addition, it was found that males are more susceptible to developing KS than females by a ratio of 5:1.[3, 1] As well, some factors such as a dry and hot climate and unhealthy dietary habits play a key role in KSD formation among Saudis.[3, 1] The influence of unhealthy dietary habits on urinary stone formation has been widely recognized in the literature.[8]

The formation of KS is a complex process that includes essential factors such as age, gender, heredity, geography, weather, dietary, mineral composition, decreased water intake and consequent urine concentration, obesity, bariatric surgery, consumption of food high in salt, sugar, and /or Vitamin C, and bowel syndrome.[9] Infections and family history also correlate with an increased risk of developing KS.[9, 10]

Kidney stones vary in size, shape, and chemical formation and are commonly classified into five types, depending on their mineral composition and pathogenesis.[10] The most common type of KS is calcium oxalate, which develops due to inadequate

calcium and fluid intake.[9] Another type is uric acid stones, which are formed due to a high concentrations of purines.[9] Less common are struvite stones, which are caused by infections in the upper urinary tract.[9] Cystine stones are even more rare and tend to run in families as a result of a genetic disorder.[9] KS can also develop as drug-induced stones caused by certain medications. In particular, triamterene (Dyrenium), indinavir (Crixivan) and acetazolamide (Diamox) have been associated with KSD. [10, 11]

KSD can cause numerous fatal complications, ranging from acute obstruction of the urinary tract to chronic kidney disease and renal failure. Furthermore, it is considered one of the main reasons why high doses of analgesic medications affects the renal functions.[11]

However, the prevention of stone composition requires a better understanding of the mechanisms of KS formation and how to avoid it.[10] Public knowledge about KS disease could help people to avoid modifiable risk factors and improve the quality of life of people already living with KSD.[1] As mentioned, the rate of KSD among the Saudi population is high, but studies on the disease in relation to this population are mostly limited to evaluating the level of knowledge of KSD causes, risk factors, and management and prevention methods.[1] Therefore, the purpose of this study is to evaluate the level of public awareness of knowledge concerning KS disease, including its causes, risk factors, symptoms, and management and prevention methods. The study also aims to explore the dietary practices and habits of Saudis, as well as the attitudes of Saudis towards their dietary practices.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Research Design:**

This study employs a descriptive research method, using an online cross-sectional community-based survey to assess the level of public awareness and knowledge of KSD. The survey was applied to a Saudi adult population during the period from June to September 2019.

Population:

General Saudi adult population, with a sample size of 1,081 participants.

Data Collection:

Data collection was done through a descriptive, online cross-sectional survey. The questionnaire features a set of 33 questions divided into the following sections: demographic variables; knowledge of kidney stone formation; risk factors for kidney stone formation; dietary habits for kidney stone formation; signs and symptoms of

kidney stones; and management of patients with kidney stones.

Data Analysis:

Data analyses involving tabulations, charts, statistical analysis and discussions were performed using Excel and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 26. Descriptive statistics were reported for sample data. Categorical variables were summarized using frequencies and percentages. Mean and standard deviation were used to describe continuous variables.

Knowledge scores were compared between categories of demographic factors. Mean scores were compared between subgroups using one-way

ANOVA (Age Group and Education) and independent samples t-tests (Sex, History of KS, Family History of KS). All inferential analyses were performed using SPSS software, version 26, with a level of significance of 0.05. Note that p-values < 0.05 are reported as statistically significant.

Inclusion Criteria:

Saudi adult population (both males and females), between 18 to 60 years of age.

Exclusion Criteria:

Any participants with incomplete data were excluded.

RESULTS:

A sample of 1081 participants was obtained with relevant details. Table 1 presents the summary of the sample data.

Table 1: Descriptive Characteristics of Sample, n = 1081

Characteristics of Participants	Frequency (%)
Age	
18-20	37 (3.4%)
21-25	149 (13.8%)
26-30	165 (15.3%)
31-35	131 (12.1%)
36-40	137 (12.7%)
41-45	124 (11.5%)
46-50	131 (12.1%)
51-55	84 (7.8%)
56-60	68 (6.3%)
>60	55 (5.1%)
Sex	
Female	849 (78.5%)
Male	232 (21.5%)
Level of Education	
Illiterate	6 (0.6%)
Primary/intermediate school	49 (4.5%)
High school	233 (21.6%)
University graduate	793 (73.4%)
History of KS	
Yes	156 (14.4%)
Male	35 (22%)
Female	121 (78%)
No	925 (85.6%)
Family History of KS	
Yes	328 (30.3%)
No	753 (69.7%)

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the participants. As can be seen, the largest participant age group (15.3%) was 26-30 years of age, 73.4% of the participants were university graduates, and 78.5% were female and 21.5% male. Furthermore, 85.6% of the participants had no previous history of KSD, while only 14.4% had experienced KSD at least once in their life (78% being female). One-third of the participants (30.3%) had a family history of KS.

Table 2: Knowledge of Kidney Stone Formation, n=1081

Urinary Stone Formation	Correct (%) or Mean \pm SD [range]
Knowledge of Urinary Stone Formation Score	10.64 \pm 2.81 [0-15]
Drinking water prevents stone formation ^c	911 (84%)
Urinary tract infection increases the likelihood of developing KS ^c	925 (86%)
Inactive lifestyle increases the likelihood of developing KS ^c	762 (71%)
High calcium and uric acid levels affect the formation of KS ^c	896 (83%)
Eating red meat increases the risk of KS formation ^c	696 (64%)
Drinking more coffee and tea increases the likelihood of developing kidney stones	574 (53%)
Drinking cranberry juice contributes to the prevention of KS formation ^c	404 (37%)
Having a family history of KS increases the likelihood of their formation ^c	581 (54%)
Drinking parsley juice prevents KS formation	337 (31%)
Most Common KS Consists of:	
Calcium Oxalate ^c	257 (23.8%)
Uric acid	380 (35.2%)
Struvite	379 (35.1%)
Cysteine	65 (6%)

Note: ^c indicates correct response

Regarding the participants' knowledge of urinary stone formation, Table 2 shows kidney stone formation knowledge scores calculated as a number between 0 and 15. The level of knowledge was categorized using the following three categories: minimal (score < 9), moderate (score 9-12), and good (score 13-15). The sample had participants with a composite knowledge score between 13-15, with a mean of 10.64 and a standard deviation of 2.81. A mean of 10.64 indicates that, on average, the participants had a moderate level of knowledge regarding urinary stone formation. Only 257 (23.8%) of the participants correctly identified the most common type of KS (calcium oxalate).

Table 3: Knowledge of Risk Factors and Dietary Habits for Kidney Stones

Characteristics	Frequency (%) or Mean \pm SD [range]
Knowledge of Risk Factors and Dietary Habits Score	2.98 \pm 1.03 [0-8]
Risk Factors	
Hyperthyroidism ^c	150 (13.90%)
Gout	366 (33.90%)
Recurrent urinary tract infection ^c	821 (75.90%)
Chronic dehydration ^c	751 (69.50%)
Family history ^c	152 (14%)
High blood pressure	183 (17%)
Diabetes	225 (20.80%)
Crohn's disease (chronic colitis)	113 (10.50%)
Bariatric surgery ^c	110 (10.20%)
Regular Diet Prevents Kidney Stones	
Yes ^c	247 (22.80%)
No	71 (6.60%)
NA	763 (70.60%)

Note: ^c indicates correct response

As can be seen from Table 3, the majority (821, or 75.90%) of the participants indicated that the main risk factor for KSD is recurrent urinary tract infection, which ranks the highest rate of the main risk factors. The second factor most of them (751, or 69.50%) chose was chronic dehydration, followed by family history (152, or 14% of participants), hyperthyroidism (150, or 13.90%), and bariatric surgery (110, or 10.20%). Also, 70.60% of the participants were not sure about the effect of a regular diet on kidney stones, while 247 (22.80%) of the participants were sure that eating a regular diet could inhibit stone formation. Overall score indicate a mild level of knowledge about risk factors and dietary habits, with a mean value of 2.98 out of 8. This represents 37% of the risk factors being correctly identified.

Table 4: Knowledge of Signs and Symptoms of Kidney Stones

Signs and Symptoms of Kidney Stones	Frequency (%) or Mean \pm SD [range]
KS Signs and Symptoms Score	2.82 \pm 1.25 [0-6]
Frequent urination ^C	95 (8.80%)
Severe pain ^C	834 (77.2%)
Increased urge to urinate a small amount ^C	455 (42%)
Fever and chills	389 (36%)
Nausea and vomiting ^C	420 (39%)
KS Affects Urine Color	
Brown	289 (26.7%)
Red, pink or dusty ^C	623 (57.6%)
Not affected	169 (15.6%)

Note: ^C indicates correct response

Table 4 shows that 834 participants (77.2%) thought the main sign and symptom of KS was severe pain. However, frequent urination (which is one of the symptoms) had the lowest percentage (8.80%). Also, 57.6% of the respondents correctly identified that urine color can be affected and changed to red, pink, or dusty. The overall signs and symptoms score was 2.82 out of 6 (maximum possible score), indicating a poor level of knowledge, with only 47% of KSD signs being identified correctly by the study participants.

Table 5: Practices Affecting Kidney Stone Formation

Practice Score, Mean \pm SD [range]	8.82 \pm 2.39 [0-23]		
Items	Frequency (%)		
	Agree	Neutral / Maybe	Disagree
Reducing calcium intake prevents stone formation	350 (32%)	532 (49%) ^{PC}	203 (19%) ^C
Drinking plenty of fluids in hot weather prevents the formation of stones	928 (86%) ^C	116 (11%) ^{PC}	38 (4%)
Salt consumption increases the likelihood of stones formation	641 (59%) ^C	284 (26%) ^{PC}	160 (15%)
Drinking cranberry juice prevents the formation of stones.	282 (26%)	676 (62%) ^{PC}	132 (12%) ^C
Drinking boiled parsley juice prevents the formation of stones.	722 (66%)	269 (25%) ^{PC}	100 (9%) ^C
Drinking barley water or barley beer (non-alcoholic beer) prevents the formation of stones	822 (76%)	199 (18%) ^{PC}	65 (6%) ^C
Lack of urination and the amount of urine during the day lead to the formation of stones.	700 (64%) ^C	298 (27%) ^{PC}	90 (8%)
Retention of urine in the bladder and refraining from urination leads to the formation of kidney stones	722 (66%) ^C	269 (25%) ^{PC}	100 (9%)
Decreasing the intake of animal protein is useful in preventing recurrent kidney stones	513 (47%) ^C	420 (39%)	148 (14%)

Note: ^C indicates correct response, ^{PC} indicates partially-correct response

Table 5 shows that participants had a poor practice score (8.82 out of a possible 23 units). Although the vast majority of the participants (86%) were aware that drinking plenty of fluids prevents the formation of stones, only 6% were correct about barley and 12% were correct about cranberry juice (as preventing the formation of stones). Also, only 19% (203) of the respondents were correct about calcium intake preventing stone formation, while 47% (513) were correct about the decrease in the intake of animal protein being useful in preventing recurrent kidney stones.

Table 6: Management of Patients with Kidney Stones

Management Score, Mean \pm SD [range]	3.62 \pm 1.40 [0-6]
Items	Frequency (%)
Best Treatment for Kidney Stones	
Drink parsley water	276 (25.5%)
Drink milk daily	4 (0.4%)
Diuretics	82 (7.6%)
Surgical intervention	212 (19.6%)
Drink water ^c	507 (46.9%)
Amount of Water That Should Be Consumed Daily	
Less than 4 cups	17 (1.6%)
4-8 cups	517 (47.8%)
9-12 cups ^c	414 (38.3%)
More than 12 cups	133 (12.3%)
Complications from Neglecting Early Treatment of Kidney Stones	
Obstruction of urinary tract and renal failure ^c	1035 (95.7%)
DM	12 (1.1%)
Stroke	5 (0.5%)
None	29 (2.7%)

Note: ^c indicates correct response

Table 6 shows that participants chose drinking water as the best treatment for KS, with 507 of them (46.9%) giving it the highest percentage. As well, many participants (414, or 38.3%) were correct in stating that 9-12 cups of water should be consumed daily. Regarding complications of neglecting early treatment of kidney stones, the survey results showed that obstruction of the urinary tract and renal failure were considered by 1035 (95.7%) of the participants to be the main outcome, which is the correct response. An overall management score of 3.62 (out of a highest possible value of 6) suggests an adequate knowledge level in this category

Table 9. Association Between Demographic Factors and RS Knowledge

Demographic Factor	Stone Formation Score (0-20)	Risk Factors Score (0-8)	Symptoms Score (0-6)	Practice Score (0-23)	Management Score (0-6)
Age Group	p < .001	p = .003	p = .09	p = .31	p = .005
18-20	10.97 \pm 3.00	3.11 \pm 1.05	2.30 \pm 1.13	9.54 \pm 2.34	3.19 \pm 1.91
21-25	11.85 \pm 3.11	3.22 \pm 1.11 ^a	2.73 \pm 1.20	9.11 \pm 2.28	3.34 \pm 1.48 ^a
26-30	11.62 \pm 2.95	3.12 \pm 1.03 ^a	2.67 \pm 1.29	8.67 \pm 2.42	3.89 \pm 1.40 ^b
31-35	11.28 \pm 3.15 ^a	2.92 \pm 0.99	2.87 \pm 1.18	8.97 \pm 2.38	3.54 \pm 1.53
36-40	11.01 \pm 3.29 ^a	2.70 \pm 0.93 ^b	2.80 \pm 1.35	8.83 \pm 2.61	3.68 \pm 1.42
41-45	11.48 \pm 2.71	2.91 \pm 1.14	2.86 \pm 1.31	8.77 \pm 2.32	3.47 \pm 1.42
46-50	12.02 \pm 3.14	2.98 \pm 0.97	2.95 \pm 1.28	8.72 \pm 2.46	3.57 \pm 1.49
51-55	12.60 \pm 2.88 ^b	2.88 \pm 0.99	2.95 \pm 1.22	8.71 \pm 2.57	4.02 \pm 1.44 ^c
56-60	12.38 \pm 2.61	2.90 \pm 0.95	3.03 \pm 1.25	8.76 \pm 1.92	3.82 \pm 1.50
Older than 60	12.95 \pm 3.29 ^c	3.11 \pm 1.05	2.98 \pm 1.19	8.24 \pm 2.41	3.53 \pm 1.54
Education	p = .11	p = .13	p = .96	p = .12	p = .47
Illiterate	11.33 \pm 3.72	3.33 \pm 1.37	3.00 \pm 1.67	7.83 \pm 2.48	2.67 \pm 1.63
Primary & intermediate	11.43 \pm 2.92	2.71 \pm 0.84	2.76 \pm 1.27	8.18 \pm 2.62	3.59 \pm 1.53
High school	11.34 \pm 2.97	2.92 \pm 0.99	2.81 \pm 1.29	9.01 \pm 2.53	3.62 \pm 1.57
Graduate	11.87 \pm 3.10	3.02 \pm 1.05	2.83 \pm 1.25	8.81 \pm 2.34	3.63 \pm 1.46
Sex	p = .013	p = .018	p = .40	p = .60	p = .68
Male	12.18 \pm 3.31	3.13 \pm 1.11	2.88 \pm 1.35	8.75 \pm 2.48	3.59 \pm 1.47
Female	11.61 \pm 2.99	2.94 \pm 1.01	2.80 \pm 1.23	8.84 \pm 2.38	3.63 \pm 1.50
History of RS	p = .68	p = .052	p = .029	p = .66	p = .55
No	11.75 \pm 3.07	3.01 \pm 1.03	2.79 \pm 1.25	8.84 \pm 2.41	3.63 \pm 1.47
Yes	11.64 \pm 3.09	2.83 \pm 1.03	3.03 \pm 1.32	8.74 \pm 2.31	3.55 \pm 1.62
Family History of RS	p = .15	p = .38	p = .017	p = .015	p = .28
No	11.65 \pm 3.12	2.96 \pm 1.03	2.76 \pm 1.26	8.71 \pm 2.39	3.65 \pm 1.49
Yes	11.94 \pm 2.94	3.02 \pm 1.03	2.96 \pm 1.25	9.09 \pm 2.40	3.55 \pm 1.48

Note: Reported values are Mean \pm SD; ^{a b c} Post-hoc analyses are reported with different letters for significant differences

Analysis results are presented in Table 9. As can be seen, statistically significant differences were found between age groups with regard to stone formation, risk factors, and management knowledge scores ($p < .001$, $p = .003$, $p = .005$, respectively). Older participants (older than 60 years) had a higher stone knowledge score ($M=12.95$) compared to participants 51-55 years old ($M=12.60$) and younger participants 31-35 ($M=11.28$) and 36-40 ($M=11.01$). Study participants in the 21-25 and 26-30 age groups ($M=3.22$, $M=3.12$, respectively) had a significantly higher risk factors knowledge score compared to participants in the 36-40 age group ($M=2.70$). Older participants (51-55 age group) had a significantly higher management knowledge score ($M=4.02$) compared to younger participants 21-25 ($M=3.34$) and 26-30 ($M=3.89$).

Study participants with high school or graduate education showed a significantly higher level of awareness (94.4% and 96.8%, respectively) compared to illiterate participants and participants with primary or intermediate education (83.3% and 85.7%, respectively), $p < .001$.

Male participants had significantly higher knowledge of stone formation ($M=12.18$) compared to females ($M=11.61$), $p = .013$. Male participants also had a significantly higher knowledge score of risk factor ($M=3.13$) compared to females ($M=2.94$), $p = .018$.

Study participants with a history of KS has significantly higher knowledge score of KS symptoms ($M=3.03$) compared to those with no KS history ($M=2.79$), $p = .029$.

Finally, regarding genetic predisposition, participants with a family history of KS had a significantly higher score in symptoms knowledge ($M=2.96$) than participants with no family history of KS ($M=2.76$), $p = .017$. Moreover, study participants with a family history of KS had a significantly higher practice knowledge score ($M=9.09$) compared to participants with no KS in the family ($M=8.71$), $p = .015$.

DISCUSSION:

This study was designed to collect information on public awareness and knowledge of KSD. Effective KS prevention depends in large part on having knowledge about the causes of stone formation, as well as knowledge of signs, symptoms and risk factors, and putting that knowledge into action. Generally, to prevent kidney stone formation, proper management of diet and a healthy lifestyle is required. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the level of public awareness and knowledge concerning KSD in general, including causes, risk

factors, symptoms, and management and prevention methods by exploring public practices and attitudes towards dietary habits. Improving awareness around KSD symptoms, causes, and management methods may help to decrease disease progression and number of morbidities.[12] According to the questionnaire, the prevalence of patients with KSD was 14.4%, and most of them were female (78%).

The study results reveal that the most frequent participants are a younger population ranging in age between 26-30 years, 73.4% of whom were university graduates. Additionally, the study shows a statistically significant difference between age groups with regard to stone formation, risk factors and management knowledge scores. Surprisingly, older participants (older than 60 years) have a higher knowledge score about stone formation.

Furthermore, although the study respondents were found to have a moderate level of knowledge regarding KSD formation, they did not apply this knowledge in clinical practice. For example, 86% of the respondents correctly identified that urinary tract infection increases the likelihood of developing KSD and 75.9% recognize it as a risk factor. As well, they correctly identified that drinking fluids could prevent stone formation, and that high calcium and uric acid levels affect the formation of KS (84% and 83%, respectively). According to Alelign and Petros's study from 2018, the most common type of kidney stone is calcium oxalate stones. This kind of stone is made of oxalate — a natural substance found in food — that combines with calcium in the kidneys.[10] However, only 257 (23.8%) of the participants were aware of the most common cause of KSD (calcium oxalate), with the majority (35.2%) choosing uric acid as the most common cause. This result is similar to that in Bos, Abara and Parmar's 2014 study, where they reported that uric acid stones are not common stones and that 93% of the participants failed to identify the high rate of the most common stones.[13]

Regarding signs and symptoms of KSD, pain was cited by most (77.2%) of the participants. Moreover, pain is associated with other symptoms, such as frequent urination, increased urge to urinate a small amount, and nausea and vomiting. These results are in line with Almuhanha *et al.*'s study findings.[12] However, frequent urination, which is one of the symptoms, was mentioned by the lowest percentage (8.80%) of participants, whereas fever and chills, which are not a sign of KSD, was cited by 36%.[12] Furthermore, the present study showed that 57.6% of the participants were able to identify KSD's effects on urine color (red, pink or

dusty), boosting the participants' knowledge level about KSD symptoms to the acceptable level.

Sodium consumption is one of the main factors in kidney stone formation. [14] Previous literature reports that high sodium intake increases the risk of stone formation by decreasing renal tubular calcium reabsorption and increasing urinary calcium.[10] In the present study, 59% of the participants agreed that a high level of salt consumption increases the likelihood of stone formation, while only 15% of the participants disagreed with this claim. This is relevant to Nouvenne *et al.*'s study from 2010, which indicated that lowering daily sodium intake minimizes the risk of kidney stone formation by decreasing sodium and calcium excretion. [14, 15]

Dietary habits play a key role in KS formation, such that a change in diet can prevent KS. Therefore, in this study, it was essential to assess the level of participants' knowledge with regard to dietary prevention. The survey results showed that 70.60% of participants were unsure of how dietary intervention could impact KSD, and 22.80% were certain that dietary changes could inhibit the development of KSD. These results contrast with those in Alghamdi *et al.*'s study from 2018, which reported that most respondents agreed that a particular diet prevents formation of stones.[1]

Another study that was conducted by Scales *et al.* in 2016 explained that moderate dietary calcium intake is associated with a decreased risk of KSD, while low dietary calcium is associated with an increased risk.[16] In the same study, Scales *et al.* mentioned that following a diet containing average levels of calcium, low protein and low sodium would reduce the risk of KSD.[16] Although the consumption of animal and vegetable protein in adequate amounts is very important for health,[14] research indicates that the ingestion of dietary animal proteins should be decreased, as this type of food increases the acid load due to its high content of sulfur-containing amino acids.[10] In line with this data, it is fair to suggest that high meat ingestion may increase the risk of stone composition, as it increases acidity.[14] Nearly 64% of the participants in the present study were aware of this effect, but only 47% of them reported decreasing their intake of animal protein to prevent recurrent KS.

Different environments, such as hot and dry climates, can contribute to the occurrence and formation of urinary stones.[12] In this study, most of the participants were aware that drinking plenty of water and other fluids in hot weather prevents the formation of stones (84% and 86%, respectively), while 69.50% knew that chronic

dehydration and decreased fluid intake are one of the critical risk factors. According to Almuhanha *et al.* from their study published in 2018, the high temperatures prevalent in the Saudi region were risk factors for a heightened rate of KSD incidence.[12] The researchers also mentioned that the high rate of patients who present in Emergency Rooms (ERs) in Saudi Arabia during the hot months of June, July and August complaining of stone colic pain was considerable.[12]

Increasing one's water intake is a simple but important step towards preventing KSD. It is advisable to drink the recommended amount of daily water intake in order to maintain urine output of at least 2 litres per day.[16] In this study, a higher proportion of respondents stated that the recommended daily water intake was 4-8 cups, which is less than the recommended daily amount (9-12 cups). Only 38.3% of the participants identified the recommended amount.

As for fluids other than water, evidence-based research suggests that drinking plenty of fluid such as citrus and cranberry juices increases urinary pH and reduces the risk of the stone formation. Additionally, drinking coffee, tea, and barley water or barley (non-alcoholic beer), which increases urinary volume, decreases the risk as well.[17] Nonetheless, 53% of the present study's participants thought that drinking more coffee and tea would increase the likelihood of developing kidney stones. It was also noticed that the majority of respondents thought that the controversial home remedy of drinking boiled parsley helped in preventing and curing KS (66% and 76%, respectively).[18] However, a study conducted by Alyami and Rabah in 2011 concluded that drinking parsley leaf tea results in no significant changes in urine composition or in reduced risk of urinary tract stone formation. Further studies are needed to determine the exact role – if any – played by parsley juice in preventing KSD.[19]

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

To summarize, it was found that the majority of the participants in this study showed moderate knowledge when it comes to KSD, causes, symptoms, risk factors and prevention methods; however, there was poor management in their practice. Therefore, a comprehensive KSD prevention program should include public awareness to minimize the prevalence of KSD and a health education program on the primary principles of treatment. A higher level of knowledge might help people better comply and manage their own care by adhering to a healthy lifestyle, developing and maintaining good eating habits, and avoiding dehydration. [16, 14]

The following are some interventional steps that focus on correcting KS misconceptions and encouraging preventive measures:

1- Clinical interventions:

- Public health education campaigns to improve health awareness and enhance quality of life in KSD patients.[12]
- Campaigns and programs that increase awareness and specifically address the importance of drinking adequate amounts of healthy water and other fluids daily.[3]
- Introduction of educational event at King Fahd Armed Forces Hospital that promotes different dietary and pharmacological preventive treatments, especially for those who suffer from recurrent stones or are at risk of kidney stone formation.

2- Dietary interventions:

- Provide adequate fluids like water, barley water (non-alcoholic beer) and cranberry juice in order to regulate urine pH.
- Avoid dehydration by drinking plenty of fluids, especially in hot weather, before going to sleep or first thing in the morning. In case of fever or severe diarrhoea, replace lost fluids. Also, decrease intake of cola and other sugar-rich beverages.[1]
- Promote maintaining a healthy weight through diet and exercise and encourage mild protein restrictions in all anti-lithogenic diets.[8]
- Consult a certified dietician, especially when going on high protein diets such as the Dukan diet for obesity or overweight management, as kidney stones are a potential side-effect of these diets. Subjects with a known history of KSD should not be on these diets at all.[20]
- Consider consulting a certified dietician to increase the intake of fruits and vegetables, as these are associated with reducing the risk of stone formation in high-risk patients.

3- Managerial interventions:

- Sustain long-term clinical intervention trials in which dietary protein is increased in healthy individuals. These trials should be carried out to determine the efficiency and potential negative consequences of a high-protein diet.[20]
- Encourage decision-makers to develop clinical guidelines, care plan strategies and educational programs for KSD patients or those who are at risk of kidney stone development.

LIST OF ABBREVIATION:

KSD: Kidney stone diseases
KS : Kidney stone

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